

Supporting information

Deconvoluting the directed evolution pathway of engineered acyltransferase LovD

Guillermo García-Marquina,^{1,2} Reyes Nuñez-Franco,³ Francesca Peccati,³ Yi Tang,⁴ Gonzalo Jiménez-Osés*^{1,3,5} and Fernando López-Gallego*^{2,5}

¹ Departamento de Química, Universidad de La Rioja, Centro de Investigación en Síntesis Química, E-26006 Logroño, Spain.

² Heterogeneous biocatalysis laboratory, Center for cooperative Research in Biomaterials (CIC biomaGUNE) - Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA) Paseo de Miramón, 182, 20014 Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain.

³ Computational Chemistry Laboratory, Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences (CIC bioGUNE), Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), Bizkaia Technology Park, Building 801A, 48160 Derio, Spain.

⁴ Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, University of California–Los Angeles, Los Angeles, California, USA – Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, University of California–Los Angeles, Los Angeles, California, USA.

⁵ Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, Plaza Euskadi 5, 48009 Bilbao, Spain.

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LovD variants sequences

Table S1. Protein sequences of LovD variants.

Variant	Sequence (Inserted mutation are highlighted in bold red)
LovD	MGSIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVIMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGNARLRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREYMAQGHLSAEKFGIQSRLAPPVNDPGAEWIYGANLDWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADQTHRNSADGRRLRYDDSVYFRADGEECFGGQGVFSGPGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGSMTFGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLAFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIIYAQYQQG
LovD1 (1)	MGSIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVIMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGNARLRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREYMAQGHLSAEKFGIQSRLAPPVNDPGAEWIYGANLDWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADQTHRNSADGRRLRYDDSVYFRADGEECFGGQGVFSGPGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLAFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIIYAQYQQG
LovD2 (6)	MGSIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVIMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGN PR LRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREYMAQGHLSAEKFGIQS R FAPP L VNDPGAEWIYGAS L DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADQTHRNS S DGRRLRYDDSVYFRADGEECFGGQGVFSGPGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLAFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIIYAQYQQG
LovD3 (7)	MGSIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVIMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGN PR LRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREYMAQGHLSAEKFGIQS R FAPP L VNDPGAEWIYGAS L DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADQTHRNS S DGRRLRYDDSVYFRADGEECFGGQGVF S PGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLAFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIIYAQYQQG
LovD4 (9)	MGSIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVIMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGN PR LRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREY V AQGHLSAEKFGI QNR FAPP L VNDPGAEWIYGAS L DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADQTHRNS S DGRRLRYDDSVYFRADGEECFGGQGVF S PGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLAFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIIYAQYQQG
LovD5 (15)	MGSIIDAA V AADPVVLMETAFRKAV E SRQIPGAVIMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGN PR LRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREY V AQGHLSAEKFGI QNR FAPP L VNDPGAEWIYGAS I DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADQTHRNS S DG K LRYDDSVYFRADGEECFGGQGVF S PGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQP E TVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCT V FFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIIYAQYQQG
LovD6 (20)	MGSIIDAA V AADPVVLMETAFRKAV E SRQIPGAVIMARDAS GR LNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGN PR LRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREY V AQGHLSAEKFGI QNR FAPP L VNDPGAEWIYGAG I DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRAD M THRNS S DG K LRYDDSVYFRADGEECFGGQGVF S PGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQP E TVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNI I WQIDPKAGLCT V FFQLEPW S DPVCARDLTRTFE K AIYAQYQQG
LovD7 (23)	MGSIIDAA V AADPVVLMETAFRKAV E SRQIPGAVIMARDAS GR LNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGN PR LRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREY V AQGHLSAEKFGI QNR FAPP L VNDPGAEWIYGAG I DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRAD M THRNS S DG K LRYDD T VYFR H DGEECFGGQGVF S PGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQP G TVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNI I WQIDPKAGLCT V FFQLEPW S DPVCARDLTRTFE K AIYAQYQQG
LovD8 (25)	MGS N IDAA V AADPVVLMETAFRKAV E SSQIPGAVIMARDAS GR LNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGN PR LRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREY V AQGHLSAEKFGI QNR FAPP L VNDPGAEWIYGAG I DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRAD M THRNS S DG K LRYDD T VYFR H DGEECFGGQGVF S PGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQP G TVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNI I WQIDPKAGLCT V FFQLEPW S DPVCARDLTRTFE K AIYAQYQQG
LovD9 (29)	MGS N IDAA V AADPVVLMETAFRKAV E SSQIPGAV L MARDAS GR LNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGL V RDETVDRLLPDL C AMPVLEGFDDAGN PR LRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREY V AQGHLSAEKFGI QNR FAPP L VNDPGAEWIYGAG I DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRAD M THRNS S DG K LRYDD T VYFR H DGEECFGGQGVF S PGSYMVKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQP G TVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPM V MRRSFGGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGS MT FGGGPNI I WQIDPKAGLCT V FFQLEPW S DPVCARDLTRTFE K AIYAQYQQG
LovD-Ch (6)	MGSIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVIMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGNARLRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS

	GLSYVFLHPLLLREYVAQGHLSAEKFGIQNRFAPPVNDPGAEWIYGANLDWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADMTHRNSADGRRLRYDDTVYFRVDGEECFGGQGVFSGPGSYMKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPVLRRSFGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGSMTFGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIYAQYQQG
LovD-Bu (8)	MGSIIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVLMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPQVDTF CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGNARLRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLLREYMAQGHLSAEKFGIQSRLAPPVNDPGAEWIYGAGIDWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADQTHRNSADGRRLRYDDSVYFRADGEECFGGQGVFSSPGSYMKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPVLRRSFGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGSMTFGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLVFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIYAQYQQG
LovD-BuCh1 (14)	MGSIIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVLMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPQVDTF CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGNARLRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLLREYVAQGHLSAEKFGIQNRFAPPVNDPGAEWIYGAGIDWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADMTHRNSADGRRLRYDDTVYFRVDGEECFGGQGVFSSPGSYMKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPVLRRSFGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGSMTFGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLVFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIYAQYQQG
LovD-BuCh2 (14)	MGSIIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAVLMARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQPLPQVDTF CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLAMPVLEGFDDAGNARLRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLLREYVAQGHLSAEKFGIQNRFAPPVNDPGAEWIYGAGIDWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRADMTHRNSADGRRLRYDDTVYFRVDGEECFGGQGVFSSPGSYMKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPVLRRSFGLGGIIALEDLDGENW RRKGSMTFGGGPNIWQIDPKAGLCTLVFFQLEPWNDPVCARDLTRTFEHAIYAQYQQG

Time-course reactions of LovD variants

Figure S1. Time courses of reactions (5 mM monacolin J acid (MJA), 2 mM α -dimethylbutyryl-S-methylmercaptpropionate (DMB-SMMP)) of LovD directed evolution variants from 0 to 24 h of reaction (**a-b**) and LovD cluster-designed variants compared with LovD wild-type, LovD7 and LovD9 from 0 to 24 h of reaction (**c-d**). Full reaction courses (a and c) and the first stage of the reaction course (b and d) where initial rates were calculated.

Michaelis-Menten plots and kinetic parameters for MJA of LovD variants

Figure S2. Michaelis-Menten plots for monacolin J acid (MJA). The experimental data (black dots) were fitted (red line) with the proposed substrate inhibition model. 2 mM of α -dimethylbutyryl-S-methylmercaptpropionate (DMB-SMMP) was incubated with 0.25-10 mM of MJA and 1 μM of enzyme, for different variants: LovD (**a**) LovD-Ch (**b**), LovD-Bu (**c**), LovD-BuCh1 (**d**), LovD-BuCh2 (**e**), LovD7 (**f**) and LovD9 (**g**). Each experimental data is the mean value of three independent replicates. The data were fitted to the Michaelis-Menten model accounting for substrate inhibition.

Kinetic inactivation parameters

Table S2. Kinetic inactivation constant (k) and half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of different variants of LovD.

Enzyme	k	$t_{1/2}$ (h)
LovD	8.082 (\pm 0.898)	0.09 (\pm 0.010)
LovD4	0.352 (\pm 0.012)	1.97 (\pm 0.002)
LovD7	0.184 (\pm 0.053)	3.77 (\pm 0.003)
LovD9	0.185 (\pm 0.005)	3.74 (\pm 0.11)
LovD-Ch	0.743 (\pm 0.006)	0.93 (\pm 0.008)
LovD-Bu	1.195 (\pm 0.004)	0.58 (\pm 0.002)
LovD-BuCh1	0.659 (\pm 0.013)	1.05 (\pm 0.020)
LovD-BuCh2	0.242 (\pm 0.007)	2.86 (\pm 0.08)

Computational data

Figure S3. Active site residues (in blue), catalytic triad (in pink; acyl group in purple) and substrate (in orange) for modelled acyl-enzyme complexes of LovD bound to monacolin J acid (MJA). Catalytic (d1-d5) and binding (d6-d9) contacts are shown in cyan and green, respectively. Bürgi-Dunitz angle (a1) between the reacting carbonyl and hydroxyl groups of acylated Ser76 and MJA, respectively, is shown in cyan.

Figure S4. Distance between the reactive carbonyl carbon of acylated Ser76 and hydroxyl group of MJA along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S5. Distance between the reactive hydroxyl groups of Tyr188 and MJA along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S6. Distance between the carboxyl oxygen of acylated Ser76 and hydroxyl group of Tyr188 along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S7. Distance between the carboxyl oxygen of acylated Ser76 and ammonium nitrogen of Lys79 along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S8. Distance between the ammonium nitrogen of Lys79 and hydroxyl group of Tyr188 along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S9. Distance between the guanidinium and carboxylate groups of Arg173 and MJA, respectively, along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S10. Distance between the centers of mass of the indole and hexahydronaphthalene rings of Trp390 and MJA, respectively, along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S11. Distance between the centers of mass of the benzene ring and aliphatic chain of Tyr148 and MJA, respectively, along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S12. Bürgi–Dunitz angle between the reactive carbonyl group of acylated Ser76 and hydroxyl group of MJA along the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

Figure S13. Profile heat map of the main tunnel cluster calculated for selected directed evolution and cluster LovD variants from molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. The first bar represents the average of the tunnels calculated throughout each trajectory. The height of each bar represents the tunnel length (i.e. number of segments constituting the tunnel). The color scale represents the width (i.e. bottleneck radii) of each tunnel segment from narrow (red) to wide (green). For wild-type, tunnels are found with a high frequency (87%) and all calculated tunnels become wider as the distance from the starting point increases. For highly evolved LovD6 and LovD9 and cluster LovD-Bu, LovD-Ch and LovD-BuCh1 variants, tunnels are found with a much lower frequency (8-20%) and the calculated tunnels are shorter and narrower. For Lov-BuCh1, found tunnels become wider as the simulation progresses.

Figure S14. Surface representation (in teal) of the main tunnel cluster calculated selected directed evolution and cluster LovD variants from molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. The catalytic triad (Ser76-Lys79-Tyr188) is shown as magenta sticks. Protein backbone is shown as a faded grey cartoon.

Figure S15. Distribution of Rosetta scores (i.e. total system energy, TSE) calculated for model full-atom structures of all directed evolution and cluster LovD variants (2000 decoys for each mutant, blue dots). The root-mean-square deviation (rmsd) with respect to the Rosetta-minimized crystallographic structure of *apo* LovD9 allowed identifying two clusters of structures for some variants (LovD2, LovD3, LovD-Ch and LovD-BuCh1-2), likely reflecting different suboptimal conformational states of flexible loops in intermediate and cluster variants.

Molecular biology methods

Table S3. Strains, plasmids and oligonucleotides used in this study.

Plasmids	Relevant genetic characteristics
pET28b <i>lovD</i>	<i>lovD</i> gene (1251 bp) from <i>A. terreus</i> cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD1</i>	<i>lovD1</i> gene (1251 bp) from <i>A. terreus</i> cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD2</i>	<i>lovD2</i> gene (1251 bp) from directed evolution design ¹⁵ cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD3</i>	<i>lovD3</i> gene (1251 bp) from directed evolution design ¹⁵ cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD4</i>	<i>lovD4</i> gene (1251 bp) from directed evolution design ¹⁵ cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD5</i>	<i>lovD5</i> gene (1251 bp) from directed evolution design ¹⁵ cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD6</i>	<i>lovD6</i> gene (1251 bp) from directed evolution design ¹⁵ cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD7</i>	<i>lovD7</i> gene (1251 bp) from directed evolution design ¹⁵ cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD8</i>	<i>lovD8</i> gene (1251 bp) from directed evolution design ¹⁵ cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD9</i>	<i>lovD9</i> gene (1251 bp) from directed evolution design ¹⁵ cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD-Ch</i>	<i>lovD-Ch</i> (1251 bp) from rational design cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD-Bu</i>	<i>lovD-Bu</i> gene (1251 bp) from rational design cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD-BuCh1</i>	<i>lovD-BuCh1</i> gene (1251 bp) from rational design cloned in pET28b (<i>NdeI</i> and <i>XhoI</i>)
pET28b <i>lovD-BuCh2</i>	pET 28b <i>lovD-BuCh1</i> gene as template (QuickChange site directed mutagenesis)
Strains	Relevant phenotype
<i>E. coli</i> DH5 α	F ⁻ ϕ 80 <i>lacZ</i> Δ M15 Δ (<i>lacZYA-argF</i>)U169 <i>recA1 endA1 hsdR17</i> (r κ ⁻ , m κ ⁺) <i>phoA supE44</i> λ ⁻ <i>thi-1 gyrA96 relA1</i>
<i>E.coli</i> BL21	F ⁻ <i>ompT hsdS_B</i> (r β ⁻ , m β ⁻) <i>gal dcm araB::T7RNAP-tetA</i>
Oligonucleotides	Sequences
V261H	GTT(V) \rightarrow CAT(H) Forward: 5' CCGTGTATTTTCGTCATGATGGCGAGGAATGCTTTGG 3' Reverse: 5' CCAAAGCATTCTCGCCATCATGACGAAAATACACGG 3'

Table S4. QuickChange site-directed mutagenesis protocol.

Components	V (μ L)	Final concentration	Step	Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	Time (min)
Water free nuclease	41.5				
10X Buffer					
reaction prof. DNA polymerase (NZY)	5		Initial denaturation	95	5
dNTP mix	1	0.2 mM each		95	1
Forward primer	0.5	0.5 ng μ L ⁻¹	30 PCR cycles	55	0.5
Reverse primer	0.5	0.5 ng μ L ⁻¹		72	6.5
Template DNA	1	2 ng μ L ⁻¹		72	10
DNA polymerase (NZY)	0.5	0.02 U μ L ⁻¹	Final extension	4	hold

Protein expression and purification

Figure S16. Sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) for protein expression and purification of different LovD variants. SE: Soluble Extract. P: Pure enzyme. MW: Standard Molecular Weight Marker.

UPLC-MS spectra of SVA synthesis

Figure S17. (a) Ultra performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) spectra of a 24 h reaction with 1 μ M of enzyme, 3 mM monacolin J acid (MJA) and 2 mM α -dimethylbutyryl-S-methyl-mercaptopropionate (DMB-SMMP) (in red), a standard of 2 mM simvastatin acid (SVA) (in green) and a standard of 3 mM MJA (in blue). The peak at 1.8 minutes is assigned to MJA and the peak at 7.0 minutes is assigned to SVA. (b), (c) Mass spectrometry (MS) spectra of the 24 h reaction with 1 μ M of enzyme, 3 mM MJA and 2 mM DMB-SMMP (negative-ion mode). The peak of 436.246 in (b) corresponds to SVA mass and the peak of 337.164 in (c) corresponds to MJA mass.